

In memoriam Dr Ottó Merkl (1957–2021)

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Abstract – Dr Ottó Merkl is commemorated by providing a brief biography, a complete list of his scientific publications, and lists of taxa described by and named after him.

Key words – biography, bibliography, Coleoptera, Tenebrionidae

BIOGRAPHY

Private life – Ottó Merkl was born on 26 August 1957 in Budapest and lived there till his death on 19 February 2021. His father, Ottó Merkl was a professional car driver, driving instructor and examiner (died in 1998), his mother, Márta Eifert was a secretary and cashier (died in 2020). He is survived by a younger brother, Gábor Merkl, electric engineer, avid collector of minerals and fossils. After attending primary school between 1963 and 1971, he graduated from Kaffka Margit Gimnázium (high school) in 1975. During his high school years he specialised in biology and in the year of his graduation he finished first at “Országos Középiskolai Tanulmányi Verseny” (a nationwide biology competition for secondary school students), earning him the privilege of choosing university without admittance exam. After completing 11 months of mandatory military service at Hódmezővásárhely between 1975 and 1976, he started his studies at Eötvös Loránd University. In 1984 he married Klára Kiss, a biology and chemistry teacher of Vörösmarty Mihály Gimnázium, a renowned high school in Budapest. They had two daughters, Dóra (born in 1986) and Boglárka (born in 1991) and became grandparents. He had less than a year till retirement, but on a Friday morning, just exiting a suburban railway station on the way to his office, he suddenly collapsed.

Qualifications – He graduated as biologist at Eötvös Loránd University, Faculty of Natural Sciences in 1981, and he earned his university doctoral degree at the same university in 1983. His dissertation, titled “Taxonómiai és faunisztikai vizsgálatok a Kárpát-medence katicabogár (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae) faunáján”

[Taxonomical and faunistical investigations of the ladybird beetles of the Carpathian Basin], received *summa cum laude* distinction in zoogeography and zootaxonomy. He received his Candidate of Sciences degree (= PhD) in 1995 for a dissertation titled “Taxonómiai és muzeológiai feladatok megoldása a Magyar Természettudományi Múzeum Bogárgyűjteményében” [Solving taxonomical and museological problems in the Coleoptera Collection of the Hungarian Natural History Museum].

Employment – Ottó Merkl started working at the Zoological Department of the Hungarian Natural History Museum on 1 September 1981. This was his first and only place of employment where he spent almost 40 years as curator, and from 1985, after the retirement of his predecessor, Zoltán Kaszab (1915–1986), as lead curator of the Coleoptera Collection. He became Head of Department four days before his death.

Fig. 1. Dr Ottó Merkl in the Coleoptera Collection, Hungarian Natural History Museum, 2018 (photo by Zsolt Reviczky)

Collection management and curation – From the beginnings his first priority was the enrichment and improvement of the museum’s zoological collections. Simply checking the roughly 7000 standard museum drawers of the Coleoptera Collection for possible pest damage is no small task, improving the rate of identification is much greater and more complex. He participated in the extensive national park inventory projects of the 1980s and 1990s. During this work it soon

became evident that identification of the entire coleopteran material collected in course of these projects was impossible without involving foreign specialists. Utilising his communication skills, memory, broad knowledge, attention to details and delicate balancing of requesting services and providing them, Ottó was great in collaborating with foreign colleagues and inviting them to provide assistance. He acquired great respect for instantly dealing with almost every inquiry he received and the payoff was a vast improvement in identification and use of the Coleoptera material resulting in valuable publications. As an example, during the years 2006 and 2007 he made 170 loans in which 30,000 beetle specimens reached foreign specialists.

Fig. 2. Dr Ottó Merkl in his office, Hungarian Natural History Museum, 2009
(photo by Zoltán György)

Collecting activity – His sampling practices require separate mention. As opposed to many coleopterists he paid attention to almost every beetle group (and collected almost all major invertebrate groups for the other collections of the museum). In Hungary he pioneered the use of a vehicle-mounted net which acquired a number of rarities, but his favourite methods remained sweep-netting and beating. The obtained mass samples were sorted on site and only a

selection of the material, already free of unnecessary specimens, was taken. This requires an extremely good eye and an encyclopedic knowledge of the species. He collected almost everywhere in Hungary, although he had a few collecting sites that he visited regularly and frequently. In the early years the sandy flats of Káposztásmegyer, later the surroundings of Normafa, the Tétényi Uplands, the Mt. Naszály, the Börzsöny Mts or the sand dunes of Kiskunság were some of his favourite sites where he collected several hundreds of thousands of specimens. He was an avid collector who picked up insects virtually anytime and at every possible occasion.

Fig. 3. Dr Ottó Merkl sweep-netting in Börzsöny Mts, 2015 (photo by Zoltán György)

Foreign expeditions, study trips – His most important expeditions and study trips: Uzbekistan (1981), Armenia (1982), North Korea (Kum-gang-san and Paekdu-san) (1988), Kenya (Mt. Elgon and Mt. Kenya) (1992), Indonesia (Gunung Palung National Park in Kalimantan Barat) (1993), Malaysia (Cameron Highlands and Pulau Tioman) (1995), Laos (Dong Hua Xao and Phou Khao Kouay) (1998), Taiwan (two trips in 2002), Nicaragua (2007), Vietnam (2016) and finally Australia (2018) which was his dream for a long time. He was collecting day and night (he frequently said that “one can sleep enough at home”) and did not stop even when he got sick. The expedition in Laos took a heavy toll on him, he got pleurisy and could not recover for months.

Exploration of the beetle fauna of Hungary – Ottó took the lion's share in the exploration and enumeration of the Hungarian beetle fauna. His dream was to compile a complete list of Coleoptera living within our borders and started this work in around 2004–2005, but this project had remained unfinished at the time of his passing away, although it reached about 95% completion. The slow progress was mostly due to the difficult groups that lacked a Hungarian specialist (e.g., Ptiliidae, Scydmaenidae, Cryptophagidae, Corylophidae, Latridiidae). His intensive collecting and research activity presented some 160 beetle species as new for the fauna of Hungary and clarified the distributions of many species previously of questionable occurrences. The current species number is more than 6350. He contributed to the enumerations of the beetle faunas of the Hortobágy (1983), Kiskunság (1986, 1987), Bükk (1993, 1996), Aggtelek (1999) and Fertő-Hanság National Parks (2002); these volumes were initially published by the Hungarian Academy of Sciences, later by the Hungarian Natural History Museum. During the same period a re-evaluation of the fauna of Bátorliget Nature Reserve (1991) provided an opportunity for completing the largest and most comprehensive faunistic publication of his early career. He published several faunistic studies, often exceeding a hundred pages, in the series *Rosalia* published by the Directorate of Duna-Ipoly National Park, treating beetles of the Szénás-hegycsoport [Szénás Hills] (2008), Naszály [Mt. Naszály] (2010), Duna-Tisza közti homokhátság [Sandridge of Danube-Tisza Interfluve] (2011), Sas-hegy [Mt. Sas] (2012) and Turjánvidék [“Turján Region”] (2018).

Taxonomy of Coleoptera – The taxonomic activity of Ottó Merkl can be grouped into three major topics: (1) the darkling beetles of the Indomalayan zoogeographic region (Tenebrionidae), (2) the long-jointed beetles (lagriid beetles) of the Indo-Australian and Indomalayan regions (Tenebrionidae: Lagriinae), and (3) the ladybird beetles (Coccinellidae) of the Palaearctic region. The research of the exotic tenebrionids and lagriines was based largely on the Coleoptera Collection in Budapest, but he was in contact with more than 200 foreign museums, institutions and individuals who lent specimens to him, many of which were returned as type specimens of newly described species. Altogether 164 new species and 1 subspecies were described and named by Ottó Merkl, the majority of these were tenebrionids; he also introduced 33 new genus-group names and 1 family-group name in Tenebrionidae. He contributed to the annotated world checklist of tenebrionid genera, which was published only after his death (2021). On the centenary of Zoltán Kaszab's birth (2015) the catalogue of the type specimens of Tenebrionidae deposited in the Hungarian Natural History Museum was published on 735 pages, providing data for nearly 6000 taxa. The rather detailed introductory chapter, providing a history of the Coleoptera Collection of the museum, is perhaps the part of the widest interest in this work. Ottó Merkl authored 248 scientific publications with total number of nearly 6500 printed pages.

Popular and educational activity – Ottó Merkl was at least as successful in his popular works as in scientific research. The monumental book *Bogarak a pannon régióban* [Beetles in the Pannonian Region] co-authored with Károly Vig can arguably be his most impactful work in Hungarian language. It won a prize at the “Szép Magyar Könyv” [Beautiful Hungarian Book] contest in 2009 in the category “Tudományos művek, szakkönyvek, felsőoktatási kiadványok” [Scientific works, textbooks, higher education publications]. It became so popular that it quickly sold out, necessitating a second edition. He regularly published in the popular scientific periodicals *Élet és Tudomány*, *Természet Világa*, *TermészetBúvár*, *Állatvilág*, *National Geographic Magyarország*, *MúzeumCafé* and *Honismeret*, earlier in the *Kertészet és Szőlészet*, *Madártávtat*, *Süni, Süni és a Természet*, *Természet, Vadon*, *Magyar Múzeumok* and *Interpress Magazin*. He had four articles in the anthology “Mire jók a természetrajzi gyűjtemények?” [Why are natural history collections important?]. Between 1996 and 2008 he wrote more than 900 entries, amounting of over 250 pages, for the general encyclopedia *Révai Új Lexikona*. The number of his printed popular articles is 137, while 111 were published online. In his writings he successfully combined enjoyable style with scientific precision. In the first half of his museum career, he translated and reviewed or corrected several hundred English language films of popular zoology while the same work on books covered almost his entire life. These more than 100 books range from high profile scientific works to books for children. Although his favourites were entomological topics, he really excelled in almost all fields of zoology. Since the beginnings (2011) he participated in the “Insect of the Year” campaign of the Hungarian Entomological Society, in which a species is selected from three candidates by public online voting. The winning species is popularised for a year in detailed printed and online pamphlets and articles. When the winner happened to be a beetle species (five times during ten years), organisational duties and most of the writing work naturally fell on Ottó, but he participated heavily even if the winner was a member of another insect order (dragonfly, butterfly, etc.). In 2020, on the occasion of the 10th anniversary of the campaign, he became a co-editor of the richly illustrated book entitled “Tíz év rovarai” [Insects of ten years]. He frequently gave expert media interviews to a wider audience in matters of interest for the entire society. Since 1995 he conducted courses in Zootaxonomy at the University of Veterinary Medicine (Budapest). He had major roles in scriptwriting for temporary and permanent exhibitions of the museum, reviewed the scientific material of these, and often participated in the realisation of the exhibition displays.

Editorial work and participation in the scientific community – He served *Folia entomologica hungarica* as assistant editor (1989–1994) and later as editor (2005–2020). Between 1991 and 2015 he was editor of *Annales historico-naturales Musei nationalis hungarici* (now *Annales Musei historico-naturalis hungarici*) and a member of the editorial board of the *Stuttgarter Beiträge zur Entomologie* (today: *Integrative Systematics*) between 2008 and 2017. He joined the Hungarian

Entomological Society in 1978, became elected to the society's board in 1985 and served as vice president from 1995 until his death. He was due to be elected as the president of the society on the afternoon of the day he died. He was member of the Hungarian Biological Society from 1992.

Awards and appreciations – He was awarded with the Bronze Grade of the Imre Frivaldszky Prize of the Hungarian Entomological Society in 1993; subsequently he earned the Gold Grade of the same Prize in 2019, being the youngest person ever awarded with it. In 2019 he also got the Pro Natura Award of the Ministry of Agriculture for his outstanding contribution in science and its popularisation. His passing away immediately triggered a number of memorial actions and reviews (e.g., SCHAWALLER 2021, SZÉL 2021a, b).

LIST OF SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS

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TAXA NAMED BY OTTÓ MERKL

Ottó Merkl described 195 new taxa, including 30 genera and subgenera, 164 species and 1 subspecies, and introduced 6 replacement names. Only 2 taxa (*Astenus laticeps* and *Carabus convexus kiskunensis*) are not members of Tenebrionidae. Taxa are listed in alphabetical order.

- Acutogria* Merkl, 1988
Acutogria falcata Merkl, 1988
Aptereucyrtus bakrii Ando et Merkl, 2014
Apteromaia akikoeae Ando et Merkl, 2014
Apteromaia butonensis Ando et Merkl, 2014
Apteromaia rugiventris Ando et Merkl, 2014
Apteromaia saitorum Ando et Merkl, 2014
Apteromaia sulawesiensis Ando et Merkl, 2014
Apterophenus nocturnus Ando et Merkl, 2014
Apterophenus sakaii Ando et Merkl, 2014
Arthromacra bhutanica Merkl, 2011
Arthromacra chifengi Merkl, 2004
Arthromacra kimioi Merkl, 2011
Arthromacra masumotoi Merkl, 2011
Arthromacra schawalleri Merkl, 2011
Arunogria Merkl, 1991
Arunogria pubescens Merkl, 1991
Asidoblaps friedrichi G. S. Medvedev et Merkl, 2001
Asidoblaps gorgneri G. S. Medvedev et Merkl, 2001
Astenus laticeps Merkl, 1991
Basanus lui Masumoto et Merkl, 2003
Belutschistanops Löbl, Bouchard, Merkl et Bousquet, 2020
Bioramix medvedevi Bai, Merkl et Ren, 2019
Borchmannia akiyamai Merkl, 1988
Borchmannia masumotoi Merkl, 1988
Bothrichara argyrostigma Merkl, 1990
Bothrichara iners Merkl, 1988
Bothrichara intricata Merkl, 1988
Bothrichara iridescens Merkl, 1988
Bothrichara wau Merkl, 1988
Bothynogria bhutanica Merkl, 1990
Bothynogria meghalayana Merkl, 1990
Bothynogria simillima Merkl, 2019
Carabus convexus kiskunensis Ádám et Merkl, 1986
Caribanosis Nabozhenko, Kirejtshuk, Merkl, Varela, Aalbu et Smith, 2016
Casnonidea apicalis Merkl, 1988
Casnonidea baloghi Merkl, 1988
Casnonidea brevimarginis Merkl, 1986
Casnonidea caudata Merkl, 1988
Casnonidea demetrída Merkl, 1988
Casnonidea dobodura Merkl, 1988
Casnonidea flavipes Merkl, 1988
Casnonidea greensladei Merkl, 1987

- Casnonidea hystrix* Merkl, 1988
Casnonidea loksai Merkl, 1988
Casnonidea pallens Merkl, 1988
Casnonidea punctithorax Merkl, 1988
Casnonidea setosa Merkl, 1988
Casnonidea tumida Merkl, 1987
Catomodontus Löbl et Merkl, 2020
Cerogria gozmanyi Merkl, 2007
Cerogria montana Merkl, 1991
Cicindina Ádám et Merkl, 1986
Cryphaeus vacca Merkl, 1989
Cyphostethe jelineki Merkl, 1991
Cyphostethoides Löbl et Merkl, 2020
Dicraeosis datangla Merkl, 1992
Donaciolagria anthracina Merkl, 2019
Donaciolagria densicornis Merkl, 2019
Donaciolagria malgorzatae Merkl, 2011
Donaciolagria medvedevi Merkl, 2019
Ecnolagria monteithi Merkl, 1987
Ecnolagria schneiderae Merkl, 1987
Ecnolagria similis Merkl, 1987
Enneboeus barrocolorado Merkl, 1988
Enneboeus brasilianus Merkl, 1988
Enneboeus rotundatus Merkl, 1988
Erodibius Löbl, Bouchard, Merkl et Bousquet, 2020
Exostira borneana Merkl, 1999
Falsonemostira malayana Merkl, 1988
Gnaptorina compressa Shi, Ren et Merkl, 2007
Gnaptorina globithoracalis Shi, Ren et Merkl, 2007
Gnaptorina himalayana Shi, Ren et Merkl, 2007
Gnaptorina kangmar Shi, Ren et Merkl, 2007
Gnaptorina nigra Shi, Ren et Merkl, 2007
Gnaptorina pilifera Shi, Ren et Merkl, 2007
Gonocnemis kondorosyi Merkl, 1992
Hangaya Matthews et Merkl, 2015
Hangaya enigmatica Matthews et Merkl, 2015
Kaindilagria Merkl, 1988
Kaindilagria forcipata Merkl, 1988
Kaszaboscelis Löbl et Merkl, 2003
Lagria amethystina Merkl, 1988
Lagria bhutanicola Merkl, 2019
Lagria brassi Merkl, 1990
Lagria gressitti Merkl, 1988

- Lagria ligulata* Merkl, 1988
Lagria paracomosella Merkl, 1991
Lagria plumbeipennis Merkl, 1987
Lagria sapphirina Merkl, 1988
Lagria schawalleri Merkl, 1991
Lagria spinulicornis Merkl, 2019
Lagria tenera Merkl, 1987
Lagria wangduensis Merkl, 2019
Lepidocaulinus Schawaller, Masumoto et Merkl, 2013
Lepidocaulinus mirabilis Schawaller, Masumoto et Merkl, 2013
Leptoderops Löbl, Bouchard, Merkl et Bousquet, 2020
Leptodes chakchakensis Tahami, Merkl et Sadeghi, 2016
Leptodes farashahi Tahami, Merkl et Sadeghi, 2016
Leptodes karmaniae Tahami, Merkl et Sadeghi, 2016
Leptodes khanensis Tahami, Merkl et Sadeghi, 2016
Leptodes persiae Tahami, Merkl et Sadeghi, 2016
Leptodes shapouri Tahami, Merkl et Sadeghi, 2016
Loxostethus erythroscelis Triplehorn et Merkl, 1997
Loxostethus gibbosus Triplehorn et Merkl, 1997
Loxostethus oblongus Triplehorn et Merkl, 1997
Luprops devagiriensis Sabu, Merkl et Abhitha, 2007
Macradesmia Löbl et Merkl, 2020
Macropodesmia Löbl et Merkl, 2020
Menimus lamdong Merkl, 1992
Metriolagria Merkl 1987
Mimoborchmania yangi Merkl et Chen, 1997
Neopachypterina Bouchard, Löbl & Merkl, 2007 (replacement name for
Pachypterina G. S. Medvedev, 1968)
Neopachypterus Bouchard, Löbl & Merkl, 2007 (replacement name for *Pachypterus*
Lucas, 1846
Neoplamius Löbl, Bouchard, Merkl et Bousquet, 2020
Odontocerotira Merkl, 2007 (replacement name for *Odontocera* Chen et Yuan,
1996)
Oreogria Merkl, 1988
Oreogria confragosa Merkl, 1988
Oreogria contraricolor Merkl, 1988
Oreogria fragilipes Merkl, 1988
Oreogria gentilis Merkl, 1988
Oreogria hornabrooki Merkl, 1988
Oreogria irianica Merkl, 1988
Oreogria kaszabi Merkl, 1988
Oreogria larvata Merkl, 1988
Oreogria lutea Merkl, 1988

- Oreogria nodosa* Merkl, 1988
Oreogria plicata Merkl, 1988
Oreogria polita Merkl, 1988
Oreogria riedeli Merkl, 1989
Oreogria samuelsoni Merkl, 1988
Oreogria torva Merkl, 1988
Oreogria vermiculata Merkl, 1988
Oreogria wauana Merkl, 1988
Oteroscelopsis Löbl et Merkl, 2020
Oxinthas nicaraguensis Merkl, 1992
Oxypistoma Löbl, Bouchard, Merkl et Bousquet, 2020
Paramisolampidius Merkl et Masumoto, 2020
Paramisolampidius csorbai Merkl et Masumoto, 2008
Paraplatyope Löbl, Bouchard, Merkl et Bousquet, 2020
Pentaphyllus cioides Kirejtshuk, Merkl et Kernegger, 2008
Pentaphyllus reibnitzii Schawaller et Merkl, 2012
Phenus atratus Ando et Merkl, 2014
Pimelia anomaloides Löbl, Bouchard et Merkl 2008 (replacement name for *Pimelia anomala* Sénac, 1880)
Prosodes fabiani G. S. Medvedev et Merkl, 2005
Prosodes kasatkini Chigray, Nabozhenko, Merkl et Kovalev, 2018
Prosodes shokhini Chigray, Nabozhenko, Merkl et Kovalev, 2018
Prosodes vigi G. S. Medvedev et Merkl, 2005
Pseudandrosus celebensis Ando et Merkl, 2014
Pseudognaptorina exsertogena Shi, Ren et Merkl, 2005
Pseudognaptorina obtusa Shi, Ren et Merkl, 2005
Rhipidandrus caesus Merkl et Kompantzeva, 1996
Rhipidandrus crowsoni Merkl et Kompantzeva, 1996
Rhipidandrus zaitsevi Kompantzeva et Merkl, 1992
Saxistena Löbl et Merkl, 2020
Scleropatroides Löbl et Merkl, 2003
Simalura maculosa Ando et Merkl, 2014
Simalura pusillima Ando et Merkl, 2014
Simalura yokoi Ando et Merkl, 2014
Sivacrypticus philippinus Merkl, 1988
Somocoelia triplehorni Merkl et Egorov, 2015
Sora barapanica Merkl, 2019
Sora lawrencei Merkl 1986
Sora marmoreipennis Merkl, 2019
Sora pictipennis Merkl, 1990
Sora yela Merkl, 1990
Spiloscapa taiwana Masumoto et Merkl, 2003
Spinanemia Löbl, Bouchard, Merkl et Bousquet, 2020

Statira baltica Telnov, Bukejs et Merkl, 2018
Stenolagria Merkl, 1987
Stenolagria matthewsi Merkl, 1987
Stethotrypes baoloc Merkl, 1992
Tagonoides skopini G. S. Medvedev et Merkl, 2001
Tetragonomenes caeruleicollis Ando et Merkl, 2015
Tetragonomenes conspersus Ando et Merkl, 2015
Tetragonomenes cylindraceus Ando et Merkl, 2015
Tetragonomenes electricis Ando et Merkl, 2015
Tetragonomenes falsocrenatus Ando et Merkl, 2015
Tetragonomenes fossiger Ando et Merkl, 2015
Tetragonomenes gibbulus Ando et Merkl, 2015
Tetragonomenes grimmi Ando et Merkl, 2015
Tetragonomenes quadricollis Ando et Merkl, 2015
Tetragonomenes saitorum Ando et Merkl, 2015
Tetragonomenes schawalleri Ando et Merkl, 2015
Tetragonomenes septemtrionalis Ando et Merkl, 2015
Tetragonomenes taoi Ando et Merkl, 2015
Tetragonomenes yamasakoi Ando et Merkl, 2015
Tetraphyllus comptus Ando et Merkl, 2014
Thraustocolus hormozganus Grimm et Merkl, 2018
Tomogria Merkl, 1988
Tomogria perlata Merkl, 1988
Trichosphaena compactilis Merkl, 1991
Viettagona G. S. Medvedev et Merkl, 2002
Viettagona vietnamensis G. S. Medvedev et Merkl, 2002
Xanthalia borchmanni Merkl, 2004 (replacement name for *Heterogria pilosa* Borchmann, 1943)
Xanthalia clavata Merkl, 1991
Xanthalia martensi Merkl, 1991
Xenocerogria Merkl, 2007 (replacement name for *Xenocera* Borchmann, 1936)
Xenolagria Merkl, 1987
Yantarozenos Nabozhenko, Kirejtshuk et Merkl, 2016
Yantarozenos colydioides Nabozhenko, Kirejtshuk et Merkl, 2016

TAXA NAMED AFTER OTTÓ MERKL

So far altogether 138 taxa were named in his honour, the majority (132) being Coleoptera, mostly (46) members of the family Tenebrionidae. The remaining six are Hymenoptera (4) and Lepidoptera (2). Taxa are listed in alphabetical order.

COLEOPTERA

- Adoretus merkli* Limbourg, 2011
Aethina merkli Kirejtshuk, 1988
Afissula merkli Jadwiszczak, 1989
Agathidium merkli Angelini, 1992
Agrilus merkli Holyński, 2018
Algon merkli Schillhammer, 2017
Alphasida merkli Pérez-Vera et Ávila, 2012
Amarygmus merkli Bremer, 2001
Ampedus ottomerkli Platia et Németh, 2011
Anisoplia merkli Baraud, 1991
Anomala merkli Zorn, 2007
Anthrenus merkli Háva, 2003
Aphthona merkli Gruev, 1994
Apterophenus merkli Masumoto, 2006
Basanus merkli Schawaller, 2011
Bioramix merkli Egorov, 1990
Borneocamaria merkli Masumoto, 1993
Brachinus merkli Kirschenhofer, 2003
Brachysomus merkli Yunakov, 2006
Bradymerus merkli Schawaller, 2006
Bryaxis merkli Löbl, 2000
Byrsax merkli Ando et Yamasako, 2013
Caecochares merkli Bremer, 2000
Caedius merkli Ferrer, 2003
Callirhynchites merkli Legalov, 2007
Calyptopsis otto Chigray, Nabozhenko, Keskin et Abdurakhmanov, 2018
Campsiomorpha merkli Masumoto, 1989
Carabus canaliculatus merklellus Deuve, 1992
Carinicates merkli Kolibáč, 2021
Cateus merkli Platia et Gudenzi, 2001
Cephalamarygmus merkli Bremer, 2010
Ceropria merkli Masumoto, 1995
Ceutorhynchus merkli Korotyaev, 2000
Chilotrogus merkli Keith, 2005
Chilotrogus ottomerkli Keith, 2007
Chlaenius merklianus Kirschenhofer, 2012 (replacement name of *Chlaenius merkli* (Kirschenhofer, 2003))
Corthylus merkli Wood, 2007
Corticeus merkli Bremer, 1992
Cryptobatooides merkli Grimm, 2015
Cryptophilharmostes merkli Ballerio, 2005
Cyclobacanius merkli Yélamos et Gomy, 1993

- Cyclotoma merkli* Tomaszewska, 2000
Cyrtosoma merkli Marcuzzi, 1999
Ditylomorphula merkli Vazquez, 1993
Dryopomera merkli Švihla, 1997
Ecnomonychus merkli Legalov, 2007
Ectromopsis merkli Nabozhenko, 2021
Emmalus merkli Ferrer, 2002
Epilachna merkli Fürsch, 1987
Euhemicera merkli Ando, 2003
Eusphalerum merkli Zanetti, 1993
Gamepenthesis merkli Schimmel, 2004
Goniadera merkli Ferrer et Delatour, 2007
Gonocephalum merkli Ferrer, 2000
Graphelmis merkli Čiampor, 2006
Hemictenius merkli Gusakov, 2004
Heterocerus ottomerkli Skalicky, 2001
Hexarhopalus merkli Bečvář et Purchart, 2008
Hoploedipinus merkli Masumoto, Akita et Katsumi, 2012
Hydrochus merkli Makhan, 1993
Hymenalia merkli Novák, 2010
Lacroixidema merkli Keith, 2002
Laena merklottoi Masumoto, 1990
Leiochrodes merkli Schawaller, 1998
Lepinaria merkli L. N. Medvedev, 1998
Leptacinus merkli Ádám, 1987
Lepyrus merkli Korotyaev, 1994
Libnetis merkli Bocakova, 2000
Macroebria merkli Lee, Yang et Satô, 1999
Maladera merkli Ahrens, 2004
Manobia merkli L. N. Medvedev, 1998
Martinella merkli L. N. Medvedev, 2000
Melanopterus merkli Iwan, 2003
Melanotus merkli Platia et Schimmel, 2001
Meligethes merkli Kirejtshuk, 2001
Menimus merkli Schawaller et Bigalk, 2021
Merklelater Platia et Schimmel, 2007
Merkli Chen, 1997
Mesomorphus globosus merkli Ferrer, 2000
Metaclisa ottoi Nabozhenko, Mackellar et Bukejs, 2021
Microbradymerus merkli Schawaller, 1999
Monolepta merkli L. N. Medvedev, 1998
Mylabris merkli G. S. Medvedev, 1996
Neoxantholinus merkli Bordoni, 2002

- Nephus merkli* Fürsch, 1994
Ochtheophilus merkli Makranczy, 2014
Odocnemis merkli Nabozhenko et Keskin, 2016
Oreovalgus merkli Ricchiardi, 1995
Paussobrenthus merkli Kabakov, 2005
Platiana merkli Schimmel, 2007
Platycerus hongwonpyoi merkli Imura et Choe, 1989
Platydema merkli Schawaller, 2004
Popillia merkli Limbourg, 2008
Priopus merkli Platia et Schimmel, 1996
Promethis merkli Grimm, 2015
Prosodes merkli G. S. Medvedev, 1996
Protostrophus merkli Kania, 1994
Pseudepisphenus merkli Boucher, 1992
Pseudobironium merkli Löbl et Tang, 2013
Pseudoblaps merkli Iwan, 1997
Ptinus merkli Švec, 1992
Rismethus merkli Platia, 2004
Saprosites merkli Pittino, 2008
Selasia merkli Kundrata, 2012
Soronia merkli Kirejtshuk, 2005
Sphenoptera merkli Kalashian et Volkovitsh, 2008
Sphinginopalpus merkli Wittmer, 1999
Stenus merkli Puthz, 1991
Steriphodon ottomerkli Telnov, 2021
Stilbocistela merkli Novák, 2013
Stilbus merkli Švec, 1990
Strongylium merkli Masumoto, 1998
Strongylium merklianum Masumoto et Akita, 2008
Synquadrideres merkli Iwan, 2003
Szombathya merkli Platia et Schimmel 1995
Taeniolinus merkli Kirejtshuk, 1998
Taiwanolagria merkli Masumoto, 1988
Taizonia merkli L. N. Medvedev, 1998
Tarpela merkli Masumoto, Akita et Lee, 2017
Therates merkli Wiesner, 1996
Therates ottomerkli Wiesner, 1999
Thorictus merkli Háva, 2020
Trichotichnus merkli Ito, 2002
Trichoton merkli Ferrer et Moragues, 2001
Troglops merkli Wittmer, 1995
Trypeticus merkli Kanaar, 2003
Uloma merkli Schawaller, 2000

Xanthos merkli Kirschenhofer, 2003
Xenoda merkli Romantsov, 2020
Zeadolopus merkli Švec, 1998
Zipangia merkli L. N. Medvedev, 2000
Zorochros merkli Mertlik, 1998

HYMENOPTERA

Bassus merkli Papp, 1998
Bracon merseli Papp, 1996 (specific epithet derived from the names of the collectors of the holotype specimen, O. Merkl and Gy. Szél)
Triaspis mervarki Papp, 1999 (specific epithet derived from the names of the collectors of the holotype specimen, O. Merkl and G. Várkonyi)
Woldstedtius merkli Vas, 2016

LEPIDOPTERA

Kisegira merkli Hreblay et Ronkay, 1999
Naarda merkli Tóth, 2021

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